

The Social and Family Attitude toward Disabled Student: A Study on Rajshahi City Corporation Area, Bangladesh

Md. Abu Shahen
MPhil, MSS, BSS

University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh

Abstract:- Disability is now a burning question all over the world. About 10 percent population of Bangladesh is the victim of this kind problem. Actually it is not a disease but a permanent situation. It is a situation when people cannot do their activity in proper way which is normal for a common people. Intellectual disability is the most victim part of disability because they are the most vulnerable group among the people and facing crucial situation in society. Typically, this study is a survey but secondary data is used at a great extent. Mainly, this study have tried to reveal the social and family attitude towards disabled student in the study area. Study reveals that intellectual disable child does not perform their proper duties due their inability and that why they are neglected both in society and family. Society does not take him cordially and behave with him rudely. In some cases, some of people get benefit of disabled child by using them. It also found that girl retarded child often victim of rape or abuse by the meanie. However, they do not get proper government support and services due to their lack of education, unawareness of society, unawareness of parents, and lack of social positive attitude. Moreover, Lack of publicity of governmental opportunities and insufficient allotment for disability are the important obstacles to develop the condition of mental retardation people. It is needed to increase government service through establishing new school for intellectual disable child, full government support for existing school, increase the amount of allowance, appropriate training and full employment.

Keywords:- Attitude, Disability, Family, Society, Support, Unawareness.

I. INTRODUCTION

Total population of the world is 7.594 billion (World Bank, 2018). Approximately 110 crore that is 15% of the total population is disabled. Among them the disabilities of one out of five are deplorable. And the total number of such kind of people who are severely disabled is approximately 20 crore (World Health Organization, 2011). Any type of physical, psychical or intellectual incapability or the failure of a person to play a desired role in the society because of social handicap is considered as disability (Kibria and Shariful, 2002). The Disables are one of the disadvantaged communities in the society and they are the victims of a thousand neglects and deprivations. Many a one think the

Disables are the curse up on the family as a result of their past misdeed. They are a burden to the family, to the society and to the state. But it is quite possible for them to lease a sound and agreeable life if effective measure is taken to ensure medical care and rehabilitation for the Disables (Anwar, Social Science Journal, 2003:79). The Disables should not be blamed for their disabilities because they themselves are not responsible for it or it is not a result of their sins committed in former birth even though the fault is ascribed to them. But they can be brought to normal social life by cooperating with them and by not sneering at them.

It should be kept in mind that disables is the integral part of the society. They also possess smooth conscience. Many Disables become famous in various domain of knowledge like science, literature or philosophy by virtue of their austere ascetic practice, Endeavour and merit. Homer, Milton, Byron, Helen Keller Stephen Hawkins, are worth mentioning among them who create several horizons of literature, science, philosophy, social-welfare in their individual arena (DUAR, 1999:01). In fact the Disables possess the same intellect as the average people. They can also contribute to the welfare of the society by their effort. Nevertheless, they are not always provided with proper opportunity to sprout their potentialities. It is true that disabled people cannot put on their attire, eat, bathe or brush their teeth by themselves. They have to depend on others for these sometimes they are not provided with proper medical care. They are excluded from various social gathering on the pretext of curse and ill omen. They hardly have the opportunity to take part in any sports or cultural functions. A positive change among most of the family members of the Disables is noticed because of various publicity regarding Disables yet the Disables are to face problems in education, health, sports, entertainment, medical care, participating in social festivals. Most of the families are indifferent to the Disable. In many cases they are ignored by the government.

Bangladesh is a developing country of the third world nations. This agricultural country is afflicted with various handicaps like ignorance, superstition, illiteracy poverty, corruption and natural disaster. The number of the Disables in Northern area of Bangladesh especially in Rajshahi City is mentionable. The Disables are lagging behind in acquiring proper education for their behavioral limitation, scarcity of their retentive faculty and the like. They are deprived of their inheritance. After the completion of

education they do not get a cooperative place for employment. They are also ignored by the Government there is the scarcity of proper rehabilitation, national survey, and opportunity of Government service, facility to travel for the Disabled, so the result is that they are deprived of their available facilities as a citizen. But today's Government is concerned about them and has taken effective measures to improve their situation. So the object of this research is to present the practical social-economic condition of this deprived and neglected community and to change the existing social outlook towards them.

II. METHODOLOGY AND OBJECTIVE

➤ *Methodology:*

This is a social survey research. All mental retardation children in Rajshahi City Corporation is included here as research population and every retarded child is selected as unit of Analysis. Simple random sampling method is used in this research. A sample of 48 disabled students is selected using random number table who was studying in two disability schools. Primary data is collected from the disabled student's family. Secondary data have been used in as per as necessity. Interview Schedule is used as a method of data collection. A primary survey is completed to collect information about age, education, income and others. Final interview is conducted after compiling the formation of questionnaire. The questionnaire is structure in nature. The possible answer is closed ended questions. For the convenience of the research, some open ended questions are also included. The collected data is quantified by using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software, version 20.0 and then collected data is analyzed by using various statistical methods.

➤ *Objectives:*

The basic object of this study is to explore the social and family attitude toward disability in Rajshahi City Corporation area.

Specific objectives are as follows;

- To reveal social characteristics of disability in Rajshahi City Corporation area.
- To explore the social and family attitudes toward disability in Rajshahi City Corporation area.

III. CONCEPTUALIZATION OF VARIABLES

➤ *Disability*

A person is considered as disable only when he fails to lead normal life desired by the society because of his physical, neurotic and intellectual incapacities. Generally, disability means the inability to do something which is normally performed by common people. In a broader sense, disability is the lack of capability to play a social role due to their physical, mental and sensational constraint and deprived from healthy and smooth social life. According to

the act (2001), A person who is physically enable or mentally disordered by birth, by accident or by ill-medical treatment and totally or partially inactive and enable to lead normal life for that inability or mental disorder can be considered as disables (Bangladesh Disabled welfare Act-2001).

➤ *Intellectual Disability*

Intellectual incapacity is not a disease; it's a limitation of growth and development of kid in an exceedingly bound age. However most of the times their growth is traditional however intellectual isn't developed as age. It's a condition wherever a child {a toddler a baby} lags behind in intellectual doing than traditional child and it's happened below the age of eighteen. Mental retardation may be a condition of subnormal mental development gift at birth or babyhood and characterized chiefly by restricted intelligence and social in-adequacy (James D. page, psychopathology, and p-354). Clearly, stupidity refers to substantial limitations in gift functioning. it's characterized by considerably sub average intellectual functioning, existing concurrently, with connected limitations in 2 or additional of the subsequent applicable accommodative skill areas communication self-care, home living social skills community use, self-sufficiency, health and safety practical academics, leisure and work, stupidity manifests before age eighteen (Encyclopedia of social service, 1995, vol-1, page-713). So, it is disclosed that stupidity is that the condition wherever kid cannot perform social behavior which is traditional to common kid.

➤ *Attitude*

Generally, perspective refers the feeling concerning one thing. This sense might be the positive or negative behavior towards one thing. This sort of behavior conjointly associated with mental and emotional entity of an individual (Richard, 2016). The person no heritable this entity through experiences that is made from a person's past and gift (Allport, 1935). Expertise that kind person's perspective is no heritable from person's atmosphere like family, society, and also the state and it influences the person's thought and action. Family plays a crucial role within the primary stage of attitudes control by someone. Primarily, an individual grows bound attitudes from his oldsters, brothers, sister, and elders within the family. There's a high degree of relationship between parent and kids in attitudes found in them. So, family's perspective extremely influence on the members. Similarly, Society plays a big role in info the attitudes of a private. The culture, the tradition, is the language influence a personality's attitudes. Society teaches persons what's and what's not acceptable. So, Social perspective towards an individual is that the most vital, distinctive, and indispensable factors to act one another (Allport, 1935). Here, perspective indicates the positive of negative feeling of family or society's members towards disabled person.

IV. DISCUSSION ON THE CURRENT ISSUES

The disability might even be a state of physical, mental, social, economic, political and all completely different fairly handicaps that a private is empty his rights, unable to satisfy his obligations to self, family, society and state, rather smitten by others for his survival (Mannan, 1996). Bangladesh is one in each of the developing countries of the South Asian region. The population of Bangladesh is concerning a hundred forty million. Considering the globe declaration and then the activities would love for services for the intellectually disabled, programs for the intellectually disabled square measure started in Bangladesh from 1977; however the services for them until recently square measure terribly restricted. Incapacity may be a universal component at intervals the human condition to that no one is immune. This draw back isn't acknowledged as a national draw back and isn't taken correct steps as a national agenda for the event of the persons with disabilities. Reasons behind this angle are low political interest and monetary profit. The comprehension on incapacity, throughout the history, has unwired on make-belief ideas. The direct results of these unimaginative image and important action by the society and policy on the persons with disabilities (PWDs) have neglected. This negligence bars persons with disabilities from ancient economic, social and political activities in their families, Communities, essential services and education. Many of us in Bangladesh scan incapacity as a curse and a reason for embarrassment to family. In Bangladesh, there square measure completely some general interventions to boost awareness of persons with disabilities at the community level. girls with disabilities unit of measurement a unit notably doubly at risk of social discrimination and neglect. The PWDs unit of measuring acceptable excluded from existing governmental and non-governmental development programs (Haider, 2007).

The explanation for this exclusion is discovered by a spherical table report organized on 2007 on incapacity. This report expressed that the shortage of applicable legal formulation and absence of materialization of existing laws direly throttle the event mechanism to betterment of the people with incapacity. They told this law titled 'Disabled Welfare Act-2001' might be a useless act. The framework of the law is simply too weak to help establish the rights of persons with disabilities. Rights-based approach need to be reflected among the legal framework relating to the persons with incapacity. The discussants put together aforesaid as an individual Bangladesh have to be compelled to reform the laws with reference to incapacity and fits the laws of world organization Conventions. Most of the speakers argued for a replacement draft of law, that need to be consulted with lawyers and totally different groups operative with incapacity (Roundtable Report on incapacity Rights and Legislation in Bangladesh, 2007).

If government does not reform with talk about with connected teams before preparing the new law on incapacity, then it remains entirely a build belief set up. The direct results of those stereo-typed imaging and

essential action by the society and policy on the persons with disabilities (PWDs) have been their neglect. This neglect bars persons with disabilities from traditional economic, social and political activities in their families, communities, essential services and education, etc. the overall objective of the study is to promote the rights of PWDs in Bangladesh by conducting analysis on the prevalence of incapacity, causes of incapacity, and state of affairs of the PWDs in Bangladesh. As a section of the study, a nation-wide survey meted out to hunt out the speed of prevalence of incapacity, causes of incapacity, and so the status of persons with disabilities and their families. A survey on the info, perspective and practices (KAP) of the people towards the PWDs was put together meted out to uncover the styles of thinking, attitudes, and behavior that characterize a given population, therefore on be able to choose a specific social development as a technique (Titumis and Hossain, 2005).

As a way of social development, incapacity is appeared as a result of the conditions where someone fails to guide a standard social life and can't play any role among the society thanks to his physical, neurotic, and intellectual inability. Regarding the character of incapacity, it's found that there have differing types of disabilities similarly as physical, intellectual, and social those are spreaders over the country and turning into a national issue. it's put together determined that these disabilities square measure increasing thanks to deficiency disease, ignorance, wrong medical treatment, accidents, nature tragedy, social disorder and so the dearth of disabled welfare and proper rehabilitations for the disabled persons. A study discovered that the rehabilitation programs area unit surpasses government for incapacity is not adequate and as a consequence, the social angle towards disabled person is not improved and stay ungratified in Bangladesh (Islam and Ferdous, 2002). A Survey on collective rehabilitation for the welfare of the disables was conducted by Bangladesh child welfare committee (2003) target the role of community bases rehabilitation (CBR) in dynamic social outlook. This survey is explored that we tend to should always cultivate positive angle to substantiate the welfare for the disabled persons. For this purpose, Bangladesh child welfare committee organize and take comprehensive informal meeting incorporates the leading feature of the society like, school teacher, Mohammedan of the place of worship and members of varied organizations below the project of CMB (Hossain, 2003). The aim was to develop the notice on incapacity among the ultimate people among the society through these persons or system. As findings of this conferences was seen expressly fruitful but the actual analysis wasn't satisfactory as a results of they was failed to produce positive social angle toward disabled persons.

Developing positive social attitude in society is very important and indispensable for the disabled persons because they are helpless in our society (Allport, 1935). A person becomes hopeless when he is ignored by his society and family. The Disables are discouraged for the lack of favorable environment for them and if the society cooperates with them they will express their total talent.

Moreover, it is seen that the reason behind their miseries is that they are not able to earn. It is also assumed that if they were employed, their standard of life would be better. Voumik (2001) revealed that the education systems is not favorable for disabled persons and the rehabilitation programs is not seen satisfactory level are run by the government of Bangladesh. As a consequence, society restricts their participation in social and occasional activities. Harmoniously, it is observed that the negative social and family attitude toward disability is not improving and socio-economic status is not changing in our society (Voumik, 2001). If the education systems were reformed and adequate rehabilitation programs were taken, it would be a better place for the disabled persons in Bangladesh.

Bangladesh is a developing and over populated country of the South-Asian region the total population of this country is 16,356,039 (WB, 2019). It is found that there is almost 5.6 percent of the total population is disabled in Bangladesh (BBS, 2015). This large portion of the total population is deprived of their right the society and leads a helpless life. They are in the terminal point of estate, power and dignity. They are deprived of the existing facilities and rights of the society. They are ignored in all sphere of society and persecuted physically and mentally. It is also seen that there are various kinds of disability in country; vision disability 32.2%, physical disability 27.8% hearing disability 18.6%, speech disability 3.9%, intellectual disability 6.7%, multiple disabilities 10.7% (National Disability Forum and Handicap International, 2005). The Disabled are part of the society but they are deprived of the common facilities and basic rights of the society. They have to depend on the benevolence of others. Family is the most important resort of a man's life. Here a child is brought up with the love and affection of the other members. But is Disabled child is the cause of dismay here in the family. As a result, he is neglected gradually and becomes a burden to the family. The family ignores their basic needs like education and health and pays no heed to their creative faculty. Family considers the Disabled can do nothing worth-mentioning. In addition, superstitions parents tend to hide their disabled child in order to maintain social honor and dignity. As a result, the socialization of the child is disrupted and opinion of the disabled members of a family is never taken in to consideration. This negligence and avoidance of disabled persons deprived them in leading a standard life in society. Every man wants to live in a society in order to develop the standard of his life. The participation of a man in social activities facilitates the development of his creative faculties. It is our moral duty to ensure the participation of the disabled in all social activities along with abides for the betterment of the society. But we look the opposite scenario in our society. Negative attitude of the society to the disabled, discourage them to take part in any social activity. As a result they are deprived of various advantages and valuable opportunities in the social and family life.

According to the constitution of Bangladesh, the state shall attempt to ensure equality of opportunity to all citizens (Article-19). But the reality is different. Though the

disabled are the citizen of the country they lead a deprived life. Their participation in National development activities is very poor. So they are lagging behind in education, medical. Care, employment, sports, culture, communication and information sectors both in local and national level. That is why this large community is regarded as a burden to the family, society and the state and they are detached from the main current of development of the country. So in is mandatory to provide them with proper medical care rehabilitation, effective education & scope for employment. It is also needed to connect them to the main current of development by creating proper scope for the betterment of the state.

13 December 2006, is a historical day for the person with disability. In this very day, during 61st session of UN a separate disabled right certificate for the disabled is passed. The disabled communities of the world are blessed with a step forward in attaining their available advantages and rights after passing this certificate. Bangladesh is an active member of this process of certification and holds her position against the separate abode for the disabled. The disabled have the right to live in and brought up by the family. Family has to take care of their health and educational responsibility as normal members of the family (BBS, 2015). Education is one of the fundamental rights to all citizens but all are not blessed to enjoy this right equally. It is observed that due to the financial inability, social handicaps, physical, intellectual or vision disability, the disabled persons are the most of them who can hardly receive higher education. But nowadays several government or non-government organizations provide financial help for the disabled. This organization also increases awareness regarding the disabled. As a result the participation of the disabled in higher education is increasing day by day. Now disability is not considered as a curse of God or a result of former sin rather it is considered as a biological handicap, ignorance unconsciousness, accident or a result of some contagious disease after birth. Specially, the disabled are not considered as a burden but an integral part to their family as well as to the society. A positive outlook emerges from the participation of the disabled in social and religious functions among the rural community, family care, and employment in accordance with eligibility.

➤ *Current Situation of Disability: Bangladesh Perspective*

The prevalence of incapacity in People's Republic of Bangladesh is believed to be high for reasons with reference to overspill, extreme impoverishment, illiteracy, lack of awareness, and particularly, lack of medical aid and services. Although incapacity may be a major social and economic development in Bangladesh, there's little or no reliable information out there on this issue, particularly within the absence of a comprehensive national survey on persons with disabilities. The government organization Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics (BBS) junction rectifier national censuses 1981, 1991, and 2001 calculable prevalence rate of incapacity at zero.82, 0.47, and 0.60 severally. However, the govt. of Bangladesh (GOB) Surveys in 1982, 1986 and 1998 calculable a national

prevalence rate of incapacity at zero.64%, 0.5% and 1.60% severally (Haque 1997, JICA, 2002). Action Aid-Bangladesh and national assistance and Rehabilitation for the Physically Vulnerable (SARPV) place the disabled population at eight.8% of the whole population. Bangladesh Protibandi Kalayan Samiti records 7.8% (JICA, 2002). The statistics on prevalence of disability has been a matter of great dialogue. Most of the estimates of incapacity prevalence usually seem to be underrated, sometimes overly. For example, in an exceedingly survey Action Aid Bangladesh (1996) records 14.04% folks suffered from a sort of impairment. In an exceedingly study by Unnyan Onneshan (Titumir, 2005) overall prevalence of disabilities has been found as 5.6 (BBS, 2015).

V. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

➤ *Types of Intellectual Disability:*

Mild mental retardation is the disability that has IQ score ranges from 50-75 and they can acquire academic skill up to the 6th grade level. They can become fairly self-sufficient and in some cases live independently with community and social support. In the study, it is found that 25 percentage student is the victim of mild retardation. However, moderate retardation individuals have IQ level score ranges from 35-50. They can carry out work and self-care tasks with moderate supervision, they typically acquire communication skills in childhood and are able to live and function successfully within the community in a supervised environment such as a group home. In this study, it is found that 29.17 percentage students is the moderate retardation. Severe retardation is the individual who has IQ scores ranges from 20-35. They may master very basic self-care skills and some communication skills. Many severely retardation individuals are able to live in a group home. In my study, it is explored that 37.5 percentages students are the severe retardation level. Profound retardate individual have IQ scores ranges under 20. They may able to develop basic self-care and communication skills with appropriate support and training. In this study, it is identified that only 8.33 percentages students are the profound retardation level. Their retardation is often caused by an accompanying neurological disorder. The profound retarded need a high level of structure and supervision.

➤ *Emerging stages and the reasons of intellectual disability:*

By analyzing the above table we explore that most of the students became disable due to their natal period difficulties which is 41.67 percentages. 37.5 percentages students is the victim of disability because of prenatal complications. Moreover, 20.83 percentages respondents argued that they became disable due to after natal causes. Moreover, it is observed that the unskilled midwife, lack of oxygen, excessive taking of drugs during pregnancy, lack of proper care of doctors-nurse, hit in the child head during birth, unconsciousness of family members and lack of proper care by the family members and lack of proper management of maternal services are the main reasons for emerging disability during birth of natal phase. Moreover, it is revealed that 37.5 percentages students became disable

due to prenatal difficulties. Lack of nutritious foods, excessive hardworking of mother, mental stress of mother, lack of proper treatment during pregnancy, lacks of consciousness are the mentionable causes for becoming disabled during pre-natal or pregnancy period. In addition, 20.83 percentage students are became disabled in lieu of hit or wound in the head, serious illness, and excessive pressure.

➤ *The treatment and education of mental retardation:*

Mental retardation is the disability which is minimized and keeps under limited level by different types of therapy and treatment. It is a situation which is improved by training and education. In this study, it is found that 62.5 percentage students took doctor treatment and 25 percentage students took more than one time treatment. 8.33 percentages took voice therapy and 4.17 percentages child took physiotherapy treatment for curing their retardation. Almost all of the respondents have taken doctor treatment, voice therapy and physiotherapy treatment. Some of the child has been able to speak through voice therapy treatment. Multi-disability that means physical and intellectual disability child has been able to increase their physical ability through physiotherapy. Moreover, there are different types of training for mental retardation child such vocational training, technical training, educational training, basic living training etc. these training provide through different types of practical activities such as wearing clothes, taking foods, taking bath, toileting, washing hands, making box, sewing, tailoring, making candle etc. In the study it is found that 58.33 percentages students has taken practical training. Educational management for retarded child has been providing through various types of teaching ways such as education through entertainment, education through keeping busy, education through counting, education through singing etc. In this study, it is explored that 41.67 percentages respondents has taken educational training from their school. Moreover,

➤ *Accommodation and the environment of house:*

In this study, is showed that about 75 percentage respondents have terraced house. Obviously it is assumed that most of them are rich. 16.67 percentage respondents live in not terraced house and 8.33 percentage respondents also live in semi terraced house. We can say that most of the respondents have a strong economic condition and they lead a healthy life. However, 62.5 percentages live their own house and most of them are educated, rich and conscious. 37.5 percentage respondents live in rent house and most of them are worker, employee, and day labor.

In addition, data is explored that 79.17 percentage respondent's house is clean and most of them are rich, educated and conscious about their healthy life. About 20.83 percentage respondent's house is not clean and they are lower class and poor people. They are unconscious about their healthy life and most of them live in slum area or broken house. However, 83.33 percentage respondents have hygienic and terraced sanitation and 16.67 percentage respondents use not terraced or unhygienic sanitation. So, it

is showed that most of the mental retarded family is careful and aware about healthy life leading. Moreover, about 12.5 percentage respondents live in noisy environment and 87.5 percentage respondents live in sound and calm, noise free environment. In addition, about 75 percentage respondent's house is made according preplan because the Sunlight and wind can move freely through their house. About 25 percentage respondent's house is not made proper preplan because the Sunlight and wind cannot move freely through their house and most of them live in slum area and also they are unconscious about their difficulties.

➤ *Relationships among family members:*

Relationship among family members is the most important factor to develop personality smoothly because it help and nourish human instinct quality. It is assumed that without smooth relationship within family members, nobody can survive on this this gently. In this study, it is explored that 95.83 percentage respondent's family has a good, sympathetic, empathetic and cooperative relationship between mental retardation child and other family members. It is helpful for the disabled child to live among them smoothly and develop his personality. It also helps to enhance their latent quality and flourish them. Data also show that about 4.17 percentage respondent's family suffers lack of proper relationship between disabled and family members. It also seems that lack of proper relationship among family members the rehabilitation and training and education cannot work appropriately.

➤ *Social attitude towards mental retardation child:*

Human being cannot live without a society. Who lives outside of society, either he is god or beast (Aristotle). Human being born in society and bring up in it. Society provides opportunities which help him to develop his personality. It is expected that the attitude of society must be positive and helpful and cooperative. In this study, it is found that 54.17 percentage mental retardation child's society has positive and cooperative attitude towards their retardation condition. In this field, society helps retarded child to take part any kind of social activities which is very needed to develop their present condition. But it is matter of regret this is that about 45.83 percentage retarded child's family thinks that the social attitude towards their disabled child is negative. They think that the members of society fun with their children. Sin some cases, mental retarded child is cheated, disturbed and wounded by a group of people in society. Some of the disabled children's family thinks that a group of people of society show their revengeful attitude toward disabled student's family from the angle of spleen.

Playing games is good to health and it helps to lead a healthy life. Different types of games are popular among the people especially in youth. Cricket, Football, volleyball, Kabaddi, Cycling, Chase, and Carom etc. are the most popular games in Bangladesh. It is found that about 62.5 percentage retarded child does not get access to play games in field. Retarded child is being deprived such kind of opportunities due to the lack of necessary skills, attractive behavior of retarded child, lack of interest and busyness of

parents, lack of playing ground. It also explored that about 50 percentage of retarded child have no playmate. They do not go play ground due to lack of their inability and disinterest to play games. But half of them have playmate and play games such as Carom, Chase and Football.

➤ *The expectation of parents and getting allowance:*

Every parent expects that one day his child will grow up and become self-dependent. Self-dependent is a situation where someone able to do something himself. In this study it is showed that about 62.5 percentage retarded child's family expects that their children will be self-dependent and lead his life independently. They also expect that government will provide employment services for their disabled child. It also focused that about 37.5 percentage family expects that government will provide allowance or financial support for their disabled child. It not possible to be self-dependent for severe and profound retarded child and for this reason they need to government allowance or financial support to lead a life.

Moreover, government provides an identification card for every disabled person. By using this card they are able to get some especial benefits from either governmental organization or nongovernment voluntary organization. Disabled child uses this card particularly for getting government allowance. Study show that about 25 percent disabled child has ID card and getting government allowance. But it is matter of concern that about 75 percent retarded child have no ID card and they do not get government allowance. It is happened due to unconsciousness, lack of education, lack of proper concept, lack of government publicity, political consideration, and opposition stand of rich family, corruption and negligence of governmental authority. It is needed to take appropriate initiatives to provide all of them ID card and full allowance.

➤ *Knowledge about disability laws and government opportunities:*

Government formulated a law in 2001 namely "The Disability Welfare Act-2001" which has been executed. This law ensures the right of disability and makes a structure for helping disabled person through governmental wings. But it is found that about 70.83 percent family does not have idea or knowledge about disability law. Retarded child is deprived of government support and opportunities. Lack of unconsciousness and illiteracy of guardians and lack government publicity are the main causes of lack of knowledge about disability acts. It also found that about 75 percent family has no knowledge about government opportunities. They do not know about government allowance, services, financial support, employment opportunities, transportation facilities, education loan. Lack of knowledge of government services for disability is one of the most important obstacles to get proper government help and services.

➤ *Vital Exploration:*

With regards to public knowledge concerning facilities offered for disables, the study by the Unnayan Onneshan (Titumir, 2005) found individuals that folks that

individuals} have very little information regarding the hindrance to employment opportunities for the people with disability. The respondents within the study opined that disables would like special coaching programme, small credit, and specialized programmes for the women with incapacity, rehabilitation services, and institution of quota for the persons with disabilities in government employment. Folks have information regarding inclusion of disabled kids and adults in education programmes, and establishing education colleges for kids with special desires. In health sector, there are a unit a point of awareness on preventing incapacity through pre-natal and delivery connected health care, polio, leprosy, and encephalopathy treatment, removal of nourishment deficiency and iodine deficiency. Some participants conjointly mentioned concerning programmes associated with noise management, pollution management, accident bar and government provided free and accessible health care because the necessities of persons with disabilities (BBS, 2015). With reference to angle towards disables, identical study found that regarding fifty fifth respondents accept disables well, 63% did not suppose that disables were a burden to the family and regarding 2 hundredth urged to present further privilege to them by providing additional security on road, reserved seats within the transport like bus, train, separate hospital, health centre, and colleges (BBS, 2015). Only a few are found to behave roughly with the disables. Once folks were asked whether or not relation with the disable folks is permissible, most of the participants replied they might settle for relationship with the disabled however ne'er allow to marry. Although folks have sympathy and behave well towards disables, they deny marrying an individual with incapacity. Although some studies found positive angle towards disables, however, many of us in People's Republic of Bangladesh still read incapacity as a curse and a reason for embarrassment to the family. Girls with disabilities are significantly a lot of at risk of social discrimination and neglect. The disables area unit sometimes excluded from existing governmental and non-governmental development programmes (BBS, 2015).

➤ *Core expectations of parents of the retarded student*

- Proper and inclusive education has to be mandatory for mass people where disabled student can take part with normal student.
- Appropriate rehabilitation steps should be taken by government with the active participation of mass people.
- Government should necessary initiatives to manage full employment of disable student.
- Disability training school should be established in every thana.
- Social consciousness toward disability needs to build as positive.
- It also needed to increase the care of their own family to disable student.
- It is needed to expand the disability allowance.

- Technical training for disability is needed to increase.
- It needed to modify and proper execution of the disability laws.
- The publicity of government services for the disabled should be increased.

VI. CONCLUSION

Bangladesh is a South-Asian developing country of the third world nations. The population of this country is around 16 crore. Among this large number of population one crore and 30 lakh people are Disables which is the 10-31% of the total population. This portion of the population is very often neglected by the society and classmates. Their life became depended to others. The disables cannot lead a normal educational life like the normal students. The main cause for this nobody is helpful to them. But the outlook of the family, classmates and society about the Disables is changing day by day. It is seen that their participation in various works of national development and in higher education is also increasing. For the development of the Disables the Government should stand beside the non-Government enterprise. Some initiatives has been taken by governmental institutions for the development of disable people such as national special education center, institution for mentally retardation child, child development center, national institution for child health, institution for central health and research, higher education various institutions. But these programs have not been playing a sufficient role to develop the present situation of disability. In spite of these programs, some non-government organization plays a role to do something for disable people. Their programs are the Society for the care and education of the mental retarded, Norwegian Association for the mental retarded, Bangladesh mental retarded welfare and education society, Association for the welfare of the disabled people. We cannot take new and effective initiatives for providing services to disable student like developed world due to our resources and lack of positive attitudes of political parties but it has been changing day to day.

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